

An Orthogonally Spin-adapted Coupled-cluster Based Linear Response Theory for Electron Detachment and Attachment Processes

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THE Linear Response Theory based on the coupled-cluster framework (CC-LRT), put forward by Mukherjee and Mukherjee¹ has, over the past decade, established itself as one of the significant methods for the direct calculation of difference energies of chemical interest, viz. excitation energies (EE) and ionisation energies (IP and EA). Applications of the theory to calculate the energy of spin-conserved singlet-singlet transitions, both in PPP framework^{2a} as also at the *ab initio* level^{2b}, have produced quite encouraging results. The successful application of the theory for the particle non-conserving excitation processes, like ionisation potential (IP)^{3a,3b}, has indicated the viability of the approach as an alternative to the other direct many-body methods currently in use such as Green function (GF) methods⁴, equation of motion (EOM) methods⁵, open-shell many-body perturbation theory (MBPT)⁶ or coupled cluster theories⁷. In the parent paper, Mukherjee and Mukherjee¹ spin-adapted the linear response equations for the singlet-singlet transitions in a fairly straightforward manner, following the usual 'loop-rule' argument widely used in MBPT⁶ for any spin-independent operator. For establishing a correspondence between this kind of spin-adaptation and a spin-adaptation using an *explicit spin-algebra procedure*, it was found necessary to identify two different kinds of spin-adapted excitation operators generating the excited state from the ground state. One set is the usual Goldstone matrix-elements used in all many-body theories involving spin-scalar operators and the other set involves reduced Hugenholtz matrix-elements which are obtained as a result of Wigner-Eckart reduction of the spin-adapted Hugenholtz matrix-elements⁸. The first set is used in the simple-minded spin-adaptation following the loop-rule and the second set is the natural candidate in the spin-adaptation using graphical spin-algebra¹⁰.

An analogous situation was noted by Paldus *et al.*^{4,11} in the spin-adapted versions of the closed-shell coupled-cluster theory and they termed the procedure using the first set as a non-orthogonally

spin-adapted one, while the procedure using the second set was termed an orthogonally spin-adapted version. Essentially, the orthogonally spin-adapted variety utilises *orthogonal sets of spin-adapted many electron configurations* for building up the theory and the non-orthogonally spin-adapted theories have as basic building blocks some suitable *non-orthogonal* combination of the spin-adapted operators which make the 'loop-rule' procedure for spin-adaptation particularly transparent. For operators which are not spin-scalars, such as one encounters in spin-adapting a linear response theory for singlet-triplet transitions, the intuitive 'loop-rule' recipe is no longer valid, nor is there any simple alternative by which analogous Goldstone matrix-elements may be identified. On the contrary, the graphical method of spin-algebra still leads to a satisfactory solution to the problem and provides one with appropriate reduced Hugenholtz matrix-elements as the building blocks⁹. Moreover, we have demonstrated that from this kind of orthogonally spin-adapted linear response theory, a suitable non-orthogonally spin-adapted version may also be constructed, provided one expresses the reduced Hugenholtz matrix-elements in terms of certain Goldstone-like spatial matrix-elements parametrised to reproduce the spin-symmetry of the problem (for details, we refer to Refs. 9 and 12 of this communication). Transcription of one form of spin-adaptation to the other is pretty non-trivial. We have found that the non-orthogonally spin-adapted version for singlet-triplet transitions involves fewer terms and is thus more suitable for computer implementation. Preliminary applications of the theory for singlet-triplet transition¹² have already produced good results and more rigorous *ab initio* calculations are presently underway¹³.

Actually, prompted by this success, we tried to extend the CC-LRT for IP calculations^{3a}. Therein we again made use of a simple 'loop-rule' procedure and developed a non-orthogonally spin-adapted theory for IP. Current *ab initio* applications of the theory along the same lines have also produced

excellent results^{8b}. But, we now realise that, as the operator involved in converting a ground state to a ionised state *is not a spin-scalar*, transcription of this theory in terms of reduced Hugenholtz matrix-elements to an orthogonally spin-adapted version for IP would again be non-trivial. This we have indeed found to be so. In fact, the graphical method of spin-algebra allows us to generate spin-adapted expressions of the CC-LRT equations for the quartet electron-detached and -attached states as well. Thus, taking the resultant spin for the ionised state as S_I , we can get results for $S_I=1/2$ and $S_I=3/2$ by a unified approach.

We present in this paper the details of the spin-adaptation procedure of the linear response theory for doublet and quartet IP's using graphical methods of spin-algebra^{10a}. For $S_I=1/2$, we also indicate its relation to the non-orthogonally spin-adapted version of the theory developed earlier^{8a}. The theory for $S_I=3/2$ is new. We also present in this paper the corresponding theory for the doublet and quartet electron affinity (EA) calculation.

Brief review of linear response approach for IP and EA

In this section, we briefly review the CC-LRT for IP/EA, which will also help us to fix the notations. In original formulation¹, coupling with an artificial photon field was invoked to compute the linear response function. It has already been shown¹⁴ that so long as we are interested in the difference energies only, a CC-LRT version in a renormalised TDA⁸ format without any photon-field suffices and this form of treatment yields conclusions which are exactly equivalent to that obtained from the generic photon-field containing 'linear-response' treatment of our theory¹. Accordingly, in this section we shall outline qualitatively the general mode of approach using this alternative mode of exposition¹⁴. For a quantitative and more extensive discussion, we refer to our earlier papers^{1, 2a, 2b, 8a, 8b, 15}.

According to this new approach to CC-LRT, let us assume that the desired ($N \mp 1$) electron ionised states are generated from the correlated N -electron ground state, ψ_{gr} , by the action of s_{I0n} . Then the EOM⁸ for the energy differences (EE, IP/EA) may be written as

$$[H_M, s_{I0n}] \psi_{gr} = \omega s_{I0n} \psi_{gr} \quad (1)$$

If we now write s_{I0n} in terms of various np-mh ionisation operator $\phi_i^\dagger$ only as

$$s_{I0n} = \sum_i s_i \phi_i^\dagger \quad (2)$$

in a manner similar to our earlier approach¹⁻³ - then the form of s_{I0n} corresponds to what one assumes in a generalised TDA approach⁸. Now, we can write the correlated ground state, ψ_{gr} , customarily, using the CC-ansatz⁷ as

$$\psi_{gr} = \exp(T) \Phi_{HF} \quad (3)$$

where Φ_{HF} is a Hartree-Fock closed-shell vacuum (reference) state.

Premultiplying equation (1) by $\exp(-T)$ and utilising the well-known CC-relation for the 'dressed' hamiltonian, $\bar{H}_M$, for the system, viz.

$$\bar{H}_M = \exp(-T) H_M \exp(T) \quad (4)$$

one easily arrives at the 'renormalised' (correlation incorporated) TDA type of working equation for CC-LRT as

$$[\bar{H}_M, s_{I0n}] \Phi_{HF} = \omega s_{I0n} \Phi_{HF} \quad (5)$$

For the sake of completeness of discussion, we can project equation (4) on to the appropriate ionised states Φ_i^* reached by the component s_i of s_{I0n} and get,

$$\langle \Phi_i^* | [\bar{H}_M, s_{I0n}] | \Phi_{HF} \rangle = \omega \langle \Phi_i^* | s_{I0n} | \Phi_{HF} \rangle \quad (6)$$

which exactly resembles the homogeneous part of the ultimate working equation of CC-LRT as advocated by Mukherjee and Mukherjee¹.

For practical calculations, we have to approximate both T and s_{I0n} . Following our development of IP calculations^{8a}, we choose to approximate T as T_2 and truncate the Baker-Hausdorff expansion¹² of $\bar{H}_M$, viz.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}_M &= \exp(-T) H_M \exp(T) = H_M + [H_M, T] \\ &+ \frac{1}{(2!)} [[H_M, T], T] + \frac{1}{(3!)} [[[H_M, T], T], T] + \dots \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

at the quadratic level of T_2 at the most. We also retain upto the two-body term of $\bar{H}_M$ (CCD-level of approximation^{8b}). For s_{I0n} , we choose it to consist of $1h$ and $2h-1p$ operator for IP and $1p$ and $2p-1h$ operator for EA respectively for ionised doublet states. For the quartet states, however, the $1h$ or $1p$ operators *cannot contribute*, since we need at least three open-shell occupancies in the determinants to generate a spin-quartet. The resulting equations under this approximation would then be spin-adapted.

Orthogonal spin-adaption of the CC-LRT for IP/EA

We write the hamiltonian H_M in normal order using the hole-particle convention as

$$\begin{aligned} H_M &= E_{HF} + \sum_A \epsilon_A N a_A^\dagger a_A \\ &+ \frac{1}{(2!)} \sum_{\substack{A,B \\ C,D}} \langle AB | v | CD \rangle_a N [a_A^\dagger a_B^\dagger a_D a_C] \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Upto the two-body term, $\bar{H}_M$ would also be likewise written as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}_M &= E_{HF} + \sum_{A,B} \langle A | \bar{f} | B \rangle N [a_A^\dagger a_B] \\ &+ \frac{1}{(2!)} \sum_{\substack{A,B \\ C,D}} \langle AB | \bar{V} | CD \rangle_a N [a_A^\dagger a_B^\dagger a_D a_C] \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

Using letters a, b etc. for orbitals and σ_a, σ_b etc. for spins, we may write each spin-orbital as

$$A = a\sigma_a \quad (10)$$

Using the Wigner-Eckart theorem^{10a}, we may write the matrix-elements $\langle A | \bar{f} | B \rangle$ and $\langle AB | \bar{V} | CD \rangle_a$ as

$$\langle A | \bar{f} | B \rangle = \langle a\sigma_a | \bar{f} | b\sigma_b \rangle = \langle a | \bar{f} | b \rangle \sigma_{\sigma_a, \sigma_b} \quad (11a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle AB | \bar{V} | CD \rangle_a &= \langle a\sigma_a b\sigma_b | \bar{V} | c\sigma_c d\sigma_d \rangle_a \\ &= \sum_{s,0} \{ab | \bar{V} | cd\}_s \langle {}^{1/2}\sigma_a \ {}^{1/2}\sigma_b | s \rangle \langle s | {}^{1/2}\sigma_c \ {}^{1/2}\sigma_d \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (11b)$$

with the property^{9,10b,12}

$$\{ab | \bar{V} | cd\}_s = \langle ab | \bar{V} | cd \rangle + (-1)^s \langle ab | \bar{V} | dc \rangle \quad (12)$$

where $\langle ab | \bar{V} | cd \rangle$ terms are Goldstone-like matrix-elements of $\bar{V}$. For the detailed expressions of the matrix-elements of $\bar{f}$ and $\bar{V}$, we refer to our earlier papers^{1,2a,2a}.

We now introduce the following Hugenholtz-like matrix-elements for the electron detachment/attachment operator, s_{I0n} ,

$$\begin{aligned} s_{I0n} &= \sum_{A \in \Phi_{HF}} \langle \phi | s_1 | A \rangle a_A \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{A, B \in \Phi_{HF} \\ P \notin \Phi_{HF}}} \langle \phi P | s_2 | AB \rangle_a a_P^\dagger a_B a_A \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

for IP, and

$$\begin{aligned} s_{I0n} &= \sum_{P \notin \Phi_{HF}} \langle P | s_1 | \phi \rangle a_P^\dagger \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{P, Q \notin \Phi_{HF} \\ A \in \Phi_{HF}}} \langle PQ | s_2 | \phi A \rangle_a a_P^\dagger a_Q^\dagger a_A \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

for EA respectively. Let us note carefully that unlike the non-orthogonally spin-adapted version of IP^{2a}, we use Hugenholtz-like matrix-elements $\langle \phi P | s_2 | AB \rangle_a$ with a 'vacant' label ϕ and anti-symmetrisation on the labels A, B :

$$\langle \phi P | s_2 | AB \rangle_a = - \langle \phi P | s_2 | BA \rangle_a \quad (15)$$

It will be convenient to look upon the 'vacant' label as a *fictitious orbital with spin zero* for the orthogonal spin-adaptation to follow.

We shall demonstrate the spin-adaptation procedure explicitly for the IP calculations. We assume that the spin-rank of the operator s_{I0n} is S_I , where S_I can take on the values 1/2 and 3/2 for the doublet and quartet states respectively. For EA, the

development goes exactly along similar lines with the roles of hole and 'particle orbitals interchanged.

The operator s_1 in equation (13) may be looked upon as a spinor operator of spin-rank 1/2 (since this does not contribute to the quartet states) so that the use of the Wigner-Eckart theorem leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi | s_1 | A \rangle &\equiv \langle \phi_0 | s_1^{1/2} | a\sigma_a \rangle \\ &= \{ \phi | s_1^{1/2} | a \rangle \langle {}^{1/2}\sigma_a \ {}^{1/2}\sigma_a | 0 \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

with $\{ \phi | s_1^{1/2} | a \}$ as the reduced matrix-element. The operator s_2 in equation (13) may be viewed as another spinor operator of spin-rank S_I and the Wigner-Eckart theorem leads to the following reduction,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi P | s_2^{S_I} | AB \rangle_a &= \langle 0 \ {}^p\sigma_p | s_2^{S_I} | a\sigma_a \ b\sigma_b \rangle_a \\ &= \sum_{S_I M_I} \{ \phi P | s_2^{S_I} | ab \}_{S_I} \langle {}^{1/2}\sigma_a \ {}^{1/2}\sigma_b | S_I \rangle \\ &\quad \langle S_I S_I | {}^{1/2}\sigma_p \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

with $\{ \phi P | s_2^{S_I} | ab \}_{S_I}$ as the corresponding reduced matrix-element. We shall now make use of the graphical method of spin-algebra to adapt the equation (6) appropriately. From now on, we shall use α, β etc. for hole orbitals and p, q etc. for particle orbitals.

(A) *The case of the doublets :*

For IP, involving the doublets, the manifold of $(N-1)$ electron states $\{\Phi_m^-\}$ consists of $1h$ states of the form $\Phi_A = a_A \Phi_{HF}$ ($A \in \Phi_{HF}$) and $2h-1p$ states $\Phi_{PAB} = a_P^\dagger a_B a_A \Phi_{HF}$ ($A, B \in \Phi_{HF}$; $P \notin \Phi_{HF}$). The equations for the $1h$ states will diagrammatically look like a block with one open line labelled as a hole-line entering the block, as shown in Fig. 1(a). Similarly, the equations for the $2h-1p$ states will be diagrammatically depicted as in Fig. 1(b) with two hole-lines entering and one particle line emanating. Using as shaded circles the one-body and two-body vertices for $\bar{H}_M$, all the distinct diagrams contributing to the blocks of Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. The filled circles stand for the matrix-elements of s_1 and s_2 . For spin reduction we shall

Fig. 1. (a) Block diagram for scattering into $1h$ states; (b) block diagram for scattering into $2h-1p$ states.

Fig. 2. Topologically distinct diagrams contributing to Fig. 1(a).

Fig. 3 Topologically distinct diagrams contributing to Fig. 1(b)

follow a universal recipe for all the diagrams of each block, i.e. we shall couple the lines (open as well as closed) of the diagrams of each block in the same manner. To illustrate this point, we shall take several examples in turn.

For the block shown in Fig. 1(a), we shall treat the spin-label indicating the rank of the operator s_1 and s_2 as an orbital with the same spin-label and for convenience treat the label as a 'hole' (this convention is arbitrary but it should be consistently adhered to for all the diagrams). Wigner-Eckart theorem applied to the s_1 or s_2 matrix-element leads to Clebsch-Gordan coefficients, a reduced matrix-element and a corresponding diagram for this matrix-element where the 'vacant' orbital label ϕ appears with a spin-label zero also, and depicted as a vacant open line labelled as zero. If we now couple the ingoing hole-line in the block and the ingoing 'hole' line for the label for s_1 or s_2 operator to a resultant spin, it follows from the graphical method of spin-algebra that the resultant coupled spin must also be zero^{10a}. While coupling, we must take care of the fact that the coupling of the open line and line for the operator s_1 or s_2 involve two holes. Thus, the coupling for the diagram of Fig. 2(a) is explicitly shown in Fig. 4(a). The coupled spins are indicated by double bars^{10b}. The

Fig. 4 (a) Spin coupling scheme for the diagram of Fig. 2(a); (b) spin coupling scheme for the diagram of Fig. 2(b)

label ϕ stands for the vacant orbital corresponding to the spin zero. The overall contribution of the diagram is given by

Fig. 4(a)

$$= - \sum_{\beta} \sum_{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} \{ \phi | s_1^{1/2} | \beta \} \langle \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} | \frac{0}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} | \frac{0}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} \rangle \langle \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} | \frac{0}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} | \frac{0}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2} \rangle$$

$$\langle \beta | f | \alpha \rangle = - \sum_{\beta} \langle \beta | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle \{ \phi | s_1^{1/2} | \beta \} \quad (18)$$

If we make use of the same coupling scheme for the diagram of Fig. 2(b), we have the coupling skeleton of Fig. 4(b). The resulting expression would then be

$$\text{Fig. 4(b)} = - \sum_{\gamma \delta} \sum_{\sigma_1} \{ \phi p | s_1 | \delta \gamma \} \{ \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha p \}_s$$

$$\times \sum_{\sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 \sigma_4 \sigma_5} \langle \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} | \frac{1}{\sigma_1 \sigma_4} | \frac{S}{M} \times \frac{S}{M} \frac{1}{2} | \frac{1}{\sigma_4} \times \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} | \frac{0}{\sigma_1 \sigma_5} \rangle$$

$$= - \sum_{\gamma \delta} \sum_{S} \sqrt{2S+1} \{ \phi p | s_1 | \delta \gamma \} \{ \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha p \}_s \quad (19)$$

For the block shown in Fig. 1(b), we use a similar coupling scheme. We again treat the spin-label on the s_1 or s_2 operator as a hole with the same spin label, and use the Wigner-Eckart reduction on the s_1/s_2 matrix-element with the vacant orbital as an open line with the spin-label zero (indicated as before as ϕ). We next couple the two ingoing hole lines to a resultant spin S and this finally gets coupled with the outgoing particle line to a resultant spin zero. We shall not explain the spin-adaptation of each diagram contributing to the

Fig. 5. Spin coupled diagrams for the associated Hugenholtz diagrams of the block shown in Fig. 1(b).

block 1(b) any further but shall merely show the diagrams after the coupling in Fig. 5. The resulting orthogonally spin-adapted equations are of the following forms,

$${}^{1/2}G_1(\alpha) = 0, \text{ for all } \alpha \quad (20)$$

$${}^{1/2}G_2^S(p, \alpha, \beta) + (-1)^S {}^{1/2}G_3^S(p, \beta, \alpha) = 0, \quad (21)$$

for all $p, \alpha \geq \beta$ for $S=0$, and $\alpha > \beta$ for $S=1$. The expressions for the quantities ${}^{1/2}G_1$ and ${}^{1/2}G_2$ are given in Appendix-I.

(B) *The case of the quartets :*

There are interesting cases where the quartet states for the $(N \mp 1)$ electron problems are actually lower in energy as compared to the doublet states. Typical examples are the 4S state of C_2^+ , BN^+ and the CH radical¹². Clearly a CC-LRT formulation for the direct calculation of the quartet states is extremely desirable. Just as for the case of the doublets, we shall explicitly show the spin-adaptation for the IP-processes; the corresponding electron-affinity calculations follow easily under the hole-particle reversal.

As indicated in the introduction, there are no s_1 operator for the quartet, and we have CC-LRT equations involving only the shake-up configurations. Using the spin rank of s_2 as an orbital with spin $S_1 (=3/2)$ and the same mode of coupling as for the doublet IP's, the resulting diagrams can be depicted as in Fig. 5. It should be noted that, unlike the doublets, the resultant spin of the coupled hole-states in equation (17) can only be triplet, so that the resultant CC-LRT equations take the form,

$${}^{3/2}G_2(p, \alpha, \beta) - {}^{3/2}G_3(p, \beta, \alpha) = 0 \quad (22)$$

for all p , and $\alpha > \beta$. The expressions for the quantity ${}^{3/2}G_2$ is given in the Appendix-I.

Transcription to a non-orthogonally spin-adapted theory

(A) *The doublets :*

We shall now show how one can convert the system of equations (20) and (21) to an entirely equivalent, but essentially simpler, set of equations derived earlier by us using simple 'loop-rule' arguments. In effect, we shall prove that the earlier derived equations are in fact the non-orthogonally spin-adapted counterpart of the orthogonally spin-adapted version of the theory presented here. As we have emphasised before, this transcription is non-trivial and involves a detailed analysis of the spin-structure of the associated operators s_1 and s_2 as also of equations (20) and (21).

Let us first note that, (i) the operator s_1 is a one-body spin-rank half (i.e. spinor) operator, and (ii) the operator s_2 , for doublets, is a two-body spin-rank half-operator. Hence, they can be written, without loss of generality, as products of suitable spatial operators and purely spin-dependent operators as

$$s_1 \Rightarrow s_1^{\uparrow/2} (1) = X^{(1)} \Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1) \quad (23)$$

$$s_2 \Rightarrow s_2^{\uparrow/2} (1,2) = Y(1,2) \Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1,2) \quad (24)$$

where X and Y are purely spatial operators and $\Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1)$ and $\Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1,2)$ are purely spin-dependent counterparts. Let us emphasise that $\Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1)$ is a one-body spin operator while $\Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1,2)$ is a two-body spin operator. Substituting equation (22) in equation (16) we find that

$$\langle \phi | X | a \rangle = \{ \phi | s_1^{\uparrow/2} | a \} \quad (25)$$

Also, using the inverse transformation on equation (17) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \phi p | s_2 | ab \} &= \left\langle \begin{matrix} S & 1/2 \\ M & \sigma \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} 1/2 \\ \sigma_p \end{matrix} \right\rangle \\ &= \sum_{\sigma_a, \sigma_b} \left\langle \begin{matrix} \phi p \\ 0 \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} \sigma_p \\ \sigma_p \end{matrix} \right\rangle \left\langle \begin{matrix} a & b \\ \sigma_a & \sigma_b \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} 1/2 & 1/2 \\ \sigma_a & \sigma_b \end{matrix} \right\rangle \left\langle \begin{matrix} S \\ M \end{matrix} \right\rangle \quad (26) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting equation (23) in equation (25), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi p | Y(1,2) | [a(1) b(2) + (-1)^S b(1) a(2)] \rangle \\ \left\langle \sum_{\text{spin } \sigma_p} {}^{1/2} (1,2) \middle| \Sigma_0^{\uparrow/2} (1,2) \sum_{\text{Spin } \sigma}^S (1,2) \right\rangle \\ = \{ \phi p | s_2^{\uparrow/2} | ab \} \left\langle \begin{matrix} S & 1/2 \\ M & \sigma \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} 1/2 \\ \sigma_p \end{matrix} \right\rangle \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

where $\sum_{\text{spin } \sigma_p} {}^{1/2} (1,2)$ and $\sum_{\text{Spin } M}^S (1,2)$ denote the

coupled spin functions for the bra and ket functions having spatial components (ϕp) and (ab) respectively. Equation (28) indicates that $\{ \phi p | s_2^{\uparrow/2} | ab \}$ is a multiple of $[\langle \phi p | Y | ab \rangle + (-1)^S \langle \phi p | Y | ba \rangle]$, because the matrix-elements containing $\Sigma^{\uparrow/2}$ on the left-hand-side of equation (27) has the same transformation property as $\left\langle \begin{matrix} S & 1/2 \\ M & \sigma \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} 1/2 \\ \sigma_p \end{matrix} \right\rangle$ appearing on the right-hand-side. We have found it convenient to introduce quantities $s_{2p\sigma,0}$ etc. through the following relations,

$$\sqrt{2S+1} \langle \phi p | Y | cd \rangle = s_{2p\sigma,0} \quad (28)$$

Also, it will be convenient to introduce quantities like s_{1a} , defined as

$$\langle \phi | X | a \rangle = s_{1a} \quad (29)$$

The parametrisations implied by equations (28), (29) and (27) allow us to go over to a non-orthogonally spin-adapted version of the theory. For equation (20), we substitute everywhere for the expressions $\{ \phi | s_1^{\uparrow/2} | a \}$ and $\{ \phi p | s_2^{\uparrow/2} | ab \}$ the corresponding quantities s_{1a} , $s_{2p\sigma,0}$ etc. and also use equation (12). It then takes the form,

$$\begin{aligned} - \sum_{\beta} \langle \beta | \bar{J} | \alpha \rangle s_{1\beta} - \sum_{\gamma \sigma p} [2 \langle \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha p \rangle - \\ \langle \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | p \alpha \rangle] s_{2p\gamma,0} - \hbar \omega s_{1\alpha} = 0 \quad (30) \end{aligned}$$

This is precisely the first set of equation derived by us in our earlier IP paper²². Let us note that the

factor '2' in front of $\langle \delta\gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha p \rangle$ indicates that the familiar 'loop-rule' is indeed recovered. Similarly, if we perform similar kind of substitutions in equation (21) for $S=0$ and 1 respectively, we obtain equations of the following form,

$${}^{1/2}g_s(p, \alpha, \beta) + {}^{1/2}g_s(p, \beta, \alpha) = 0 \quad (31a)$$

$${}^{1/2}g_s(p, \alpha, \beta) - {}^{1/2}g_s(p, \beta, \alpha) = 0 \text{ for } p, \alpha \geq \beta, \quad (31b)$$

wherefrom we get simpler equations,

$${}^{1/2}g_s(p, \alpha, \beta) = 0, \quad (32)$$

for all p, α, β . The expression for ${}^{1/2}g_s(p, \alpha, \beta)$ can be written down again if we substitute the values of appropriate $9j$'s and $6j$'s given in the Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The expression has been collected in Appendix-II(A). A close examination of the expression for ${}^{1/2}g_s(p, \alpha, \beta)$ shows that it is precisely identical with the second set of equation in our earlier IP paper^{2a}.

TABLE 1—LIST OF $9j$ VALUES

Form 1 :			
S	S_1	S_2	Value
0	0	0	-1/4
0	1	0	1/4
0	0	1	1/4
0	1	1	1/12
1	0	1	1/12
1	0	0	1/4
1	1	0	1/12
1	1	1	5/36

Form 2 :			
S	S_1	S_2	Value
1	0	1	-1/6
1	1	1	1/18

TABLE 2—LIST OF $6j$ VALUES

Form 1 :			
S_1	S	S_2	Value
0	0	0	-1/2
0	1	0	1/2
1	0	0	1/2
1	1	0	1/6

Form 2 :			
S	S_1	S_2	Value
0	0	0	-1/√2
0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0
0	1	1	1/√6
1	0	0	0
1	1	0	1/√6
1	0	1	1/√6
1	1	1	-1/3

The crux of our exercise lies in the observations that the usual loop-rule is valid for a spin operator of rank half (doublet IP/EA) and that 'the non-orthogonally spin-adapted version follows' from the rigorously derived orthogonally spin-adapted version of the theory through a linear transformation implied by the parametrisations introduced in equations (25) to (29). We conclude this section by commenting that an entirely analogous development follows for EA calculations as well, with a consequently similar parametrisation originating from equation (14). The key quantities will then be the matrix elements s_{1p} and $s_{sp,q,\alpha}$. The explicit equations for EA (doublet) in non-orthogonally spin-adapted form have been collected in Appendix-III(A).

(B) *The quartets :*

For the quartets, the s_1 -amplitudes will vanish due to the restrictions in spin-coupling; it is impossible to couple an electron of spin-half with an operator of rank 3/2 to form another doublet state. For the model we are advocating, the only amplitudes are those for the s_s -operators. In a way analogous to what was done in equation (24), we may write an s_s -operator of rank 3/2 as

$$s_s \Rightarrow s_s^{3/2}(1,2) = Y(1,2) \Sigma_s^{3/2}(1,2) \quad (33)$$

where $Y(1,2)$ is a spatial operator and $\Sigma_s^{3/2}(1,2)$ is a pure spin operator. Using manipulations similar to those encountered in equations (26) and (27), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \phi p | Y(1,2) | [a(1)b(2) + (-1)^S b(1)a(2)] \rangle \\ \langle \Sigma_s^{1/2}(1,2) | \Sigma_M^S(1,2) \rangle \\ = \langle \phi p | s_s^{3/2} | ab \rangle \langle \Sigma_M^{s/2} | \Sigma_s^{1/2} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Since the Clebsch-Gordan coefficient in equation (34) is non-zero for $S=1$ and zero for $S=0$, it follows that the relevant reduced matrix-element in equation (34) is for $S=1$ only. Moreover, this must have the form,

$$\langle \phi p | s_s^{3/2} | ab \rangle = \text{factor} \times [\langle \phi p | Y | ab \rangle - \langle \phi p | Y | ba \rangle] \quad (35)$$

It has been found convenient to assign a value of $\sqrt{3}$ to this factor, and rewrite equation (35) as

$$\langle \phi p | s_s^{3/2} | ab \rangle = \sqrt{3} s_{s,p,s,b} \quad (36)$$

Let us now take a close look at the structure of the CC-LRT equations for the quartets. The equations are of the form,

$$G_s^{3/2}(p, \alpha, \beta) - G_s^{3/2}(p, \beta, \alpha) = 0 \quad (37)$$

all $p, \alpha > \beta$. The expression for ${}^{3/2}G_s(p, \alpha, \beta)$ is given in Appendix-I. Equation (37) corresponds to the orthogonally spin-adapted version for the quartets. In order to transcribe it to the non-orthogonally spin-adapted form, we are left with two possible choices. Since equation (35) implies that the

reduced matrix-element depends on the *difference* of two Goldstone-like entities $\langle \phi_p | Y | ab \rangle$ and $\langle \phi_p | Y | ba \rangle$, we can give a common shift $x_{p,a,b}$ to each of these two without changing the value of $\{\phi_p | s_a^{3/2} | ab \}_1$. Thus, we can have two distinct useful possibilities :

Choice 1 : We choose $x_{p,a,b}$ in such a way that

$${}^{3/2}G_s(p,\alpha,\beta)=0, \text{ for } \alpha > \beta \quad (38a)$$

Equation (37) then implies that

$${}^{3/2}G_s(p,\beta,\alpha)=0, \text{ for } \alpha < \beta \quad (38b)$$

Thus, we have two equations, (38a) and (38b), for each pair (α,β) , $\alpha > \beta$, and correspondingly we have two unknowns $\langle \phi_p | Y | \alpha\beta \rangle$ and $\langle \phi_p | Y | \beta\alpha \rangle$.

Choice 2 : We choose $x_{p,a,b}$ in such a way that $\langle \phi_p | Y | \beta\alpha \rangle = 0$. In that case $s_{s,p,\alpha,\beta}$ is the only unknown for $\alpha > \beta$. Equation (37), written out in terms of Goldstone matrix-elements, can be rewritten as

$${}^{3/2}g_s(p,\alpha,\beta) - {}^{3/2}g_s(p,\beta,\alpha) = 0 \quad (39)$$

all $p, \alpha > \beta$. The expression for ${}^{3/2}g_s(p,\alpha,\beta)$ is collected in Appendix-II.

Since the choice 2 leads to precisely the same number of variables as the original orthogonally spin-adapted form, we would prefer to use the latter. It should be noted that $s_{s,p,\alpha,\beta}$ is antisymmetric in the indices a and b (vide equation (35)).

Concluding remarks

The formalism presented here is currently being applied both for the doublet and the quartet electron detachment and attachment processes¹³. Since the CC-LRT incorporates product excitations of the form ST, $\frac{ST}{(2!)}$ etc., it involves a simulation of multiple excitations in the ionised states without actually proliferating the ionisation operator manifold.

It should be mentioned that for the quartet ionised states, there are three open-shell orbitals. A proper description of the size extensivity of the ionised states requires a *complete cluster-expansion structure* of the respective functions¹⁵. The CC-LRT, on the other hand, involves a *hybrid structure*¹⁴—an explicit cluster-structure involving the cluster operators ($\exp(T_a)$) of the ground state and a linear operator structure (as in CI) for the correlations involving the open-shell orbitals. Thus, the correlation of the ground state ('core') is completely size-extensive, but the correlation change involving the ionisation is not strictly so.—Consequently, the theory may be termed as a 'core-extensive theory'¹⁶, and is likely to be applicationally quite good so long as the total number of electrons is much larger than three, the number of open-shells in the ionised states. For a general discussion of the extensivity problem, we refer to a recent comprehensive survey¹⁷.

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Appendix-I

Here we have collected the expressions for the quantities $G_1(\alpha)$ and ${}^I G_s^g(p,\alpha,\beta)$ appearing in equations (20), (21) and (22), where S_I corresponds to the spin rank of the operator s_s and can have values 1/2 and 3/2 respectively for the doublet and the quartet spin states.

$$(A) G_1(\alpha) = -\sum_{\gamma} \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle \{ \phi | s_1 | \gamma \} -$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_S \sqrt{2S+1} \sum_{\gamma, \delta, r} \{ \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha r \}_S \left\{ \phi r \left| \begin{matrix} S_I \\ s_s \end{matrix} \right| \delta \gamma \right\}_S - \hbar \omega \{ \phi | s_1 | \alpha \} \quad (I.1)$$

$$(B) {}^I G_s^g(p,\alpha,\beta) = \sqrt{2} \left[\sum_r \langle p | \bar{f} | r \rangle \left\{ \phi r \left| \begin{matrix} S_I \\ s_s \end{matrix} \right| \beta \alpha \right\}_S - \right.$$

$$\sum_{\gamma} \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \beta \rangle \left\{ \phi p \left| \begin{matrix} S_I \\ s_s \end{matrix} \right| \gamma \alpha \right\}_S -$$

$$\left. \sum_{\delta} \langle \delta | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle \left\{ \phi p \left| \begin{matrix} S_I \\ s_s \end{matrix} \right| \beta \delta \right\}_S \right] +$$

$$\sqrt{2} \sum_{S_1 S_2} (-1)^{1+S_1+S_2} [S] [S_1^2] [S_2] \begin{bmatrix} S_s & S_I & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & 1/2 & S_1 \\ 1/2 & S_2 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\times \sum_{\gamma, r} \{ p \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha r \}_{S_1} \{ \phi r | s_s^I | \beta \gamma \}_{S_2} +$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{\gamma, \delta} \{ \delta \gamma | \bar{V} | \beta \alpha \}_S \{ \phi p | s_s^I | \delta \gamma \}_S -$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{2S+1}{2}} \sum_{\gamma, \alpha} \{ \gamma p | \bar{V} | \beta \alpha \}_S \{ \phi | s_1 | \gamma \} -$$

$$\sqrt{2} \hbar \omega \{ \phi p | s_s^I | \beta \alpha \}_S \quad (I.2)$$

Appendix-II

Here we have collected the expressions for ${}^{1/2}g_s(p,\alpha,\beta)$ and ${}^{3/2}g_s(p,\alpha,\beta)$ appearing in equations (32) and (39) for doublet and quartet spin states respectively.

$$(A) {}^{1/2}g_s(p,\alpha,\beta) = -\sum_{\gamma, q} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | \beta \alpha \rangle s_{1\gamma} + \sum_{\alpha, \delta} 2 \langle p \delta | \bar{V} | \alpha q \rangle -$$

$$\langle p \delta | \bar{V} | q \alpha \rangle \}_{s_{s,q,\alpha,\beta}} +$$

$$\sum_{\gamma, \delta} \langle \gamma \delta | \bar{V} | \alpha \beta \rangle s_{s,p,\gamma,\delta} -$$

$$\sum_{\alpha, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha q \rangle s_{s,q,\beta,\gamma} +$$

$$\langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | q \alpha \rangle \}_{s_{s,q,\beta,\gamma}} -$$

$$\sum_{\gamma} \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle s_{s,p,\gamma,\beta} + \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \beta \rangle s_{s,p,\alpha,\gamma} \}_{s_{s,p,\alpha,\beta}} +$$

$$\sum_{\alpha} \langle p | \bar{f} | q \rangle s_{s,q,\alpha,\beta} - \hbar \omega s_{s,p,\alpha,\beta} \quad (II.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(B)} \quad & {}^{1/2}g_3(p, \alpha, \beta) \\
 & = \sum_q \langle p | \bar{f} | q \rangle s_{s_{q, \alpha, \beta}} - \sum_\gamma \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle s_{s_{p, \gamma, \beta}} - \\
 & \sum_\gamma \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \beta \rangle s_{s_{p, \alpha, \gamma}} + \sum_{\gamma, \delta} \langle \gamma \delta | \bar{V} | \alpha \beta \rangle s_{s_{p, \gamma, \delta}} - \\
 & \sum_{\gamma, \alpha} [\langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | q \alpha \rangle s_{s_{p, \gamma, \beta}} - \\
 & \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | q \alpha \rangle s_{s_{p, \beta, \gamma}}] - \hbar \omega s_{s_{p, \alpha, \beta}} \\
 & = \sum_q \langle p | \bar{f} | q \rangle s_{s_{q, \alpha, \beta}} - \sum_\gamma \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle s_{s_{p, \gamma, \beta}} - \\
 & \sum_\gamma \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \beta \rangle s_{s_{p, \alpha, \gamma}} + \sum_{\gamma, \delta} \langle \gamma \delta | \bar{V} | \alpha \beta \rangle s_{s_{p, \gamma, \delta}} - \\
 & \sum_{q, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | q \alpha \rangle s_{s_{q, \gamma, \beta}} - \\
 & \sum_{q, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | q \beta \rangle s_{s_{q, \alpha, \gamma}} - \hbar \omega s_{s_{p, \alpha, \beta}} \quad \text{(II 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Appendix-III

Here we have collected the ultimate expressions corresponding to the electron detachment (EA) process, for both the doublet and quartet spin states, in non-orthogonally spin-adapted form.

(A) For doublet

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^{1/2}g_1(p) & = \sum_r \langle p | \bar{f} | r \rangle s_{1r} + \sum_{r, s, \gamma} [2 \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | rs \rangle - \\
 & \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | sr \rangle] s_{s_{r, s, \gamma}} - \hbar \omega s_{1p} \quad \text{(III.A.1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

${}^{1/2}g_3(q, p, \alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & = \sum_{r, \gamma} [2 \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha r \rangle - \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | r \alpha \rangle] s_{s_{r, q, \gamma}} - \\
 & \sum_{r, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha r \rangle s_{s_{r, q, \gamma}} + \\
 & \sum_{r, s} \langle qp | \bar{V} | rs \rangle s_{s_{r, s, \alpha}} + \sum_r \langle qp | \bar{V} | r \alpha \rangle s_{1r} - \\
 & \sum_{r, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | r \alpha \rangle s_{s_{r, q, \gamma}} + \sum_r \langle q | \bar{f} | r \rangle s_{s_{r, p, \alpha}} + \\
 & \sum_s \langle p | \bar{f} | s \rangle s_{s_{q, s, \alpha}} - \sum_r \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle s_{s_{q, d, \gamma}} - \\
 & \hbar \omega s_{s_{q, d, \alpha}} \quad \text{(III.A.2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

(B) For quartet

${}^{3/2}g_1(p) = 0$

${}^{3/2}g_3(q, p, \alpha)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & = \sum_r \langle q | \bar{f} | r \rangle s_{s_{r, d, \alpha}} + \sum_s \langle p | \bar{f} | s \rangle s_{s_{q, s, \alpha}} - \\
 & \sum_\gamma \langle \gamma | \bar{f} | \alpha \rangle s_{s_{q, \gamma, \alpha}} + \sum_{r, s} \langle qp | \bar{V} | rs \rangle s_{s_{r, s, \alpha}} - \\
 & \sum_{r, \gamma} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | \alpha r \rangle s_{s_{r, q, \gamma}} - \sum_{r, s} \langle p \gamma | \bar{V} | r \alpha \rangle s_{s_{r, q, \gamma}} - \\
 & \hbar \omega s_{s_{q, d, \alpha}} \quad \text{(III.B.2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

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